

**MODERN APPROACHES TO OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH
AND SAFETY**

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In the field of labor protection and technical safety.

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Abstract. This article discusses issues of labor protection and ensuring constant safety in the production and service sectors, labor legislation, safety rules, risk assessment at the workplace, industrial hygiene, personal protective equipment, accident prevention and the use of digital technologies, scientific, theoretical and practical analysis. The main components of the occupational safety and health system, methods for identifying and assessing risk factors, as well as modern approaches to emergency prevention will be considered. The study will draw analytical conclusions based on regulations, best foreign practices and real production conditions. The results will contribute to improving working conditions, improving safety culture in production processes and ensuring sustainable development.

Keywords: labor protection, production safety, technosphere safety, risk factors, industrial safety.

**MEHNATNI HIMOYALASH VA DOIMIY XAVFSIZLIKNI
TA'MINLASHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUV USULLARI**

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Mehnat muhofazasi va texnika xavfsizligi fanidan.

Farg'ona viloyati Beshariq tumani 2 – son texnikumi

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ishlab chiqarish va xizmat ko'rsatish sohalarida mehnatni himoyalash hamda doimiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlash masalalari, mehnat

qonunchiligi, texnika xavfsizligi qoidalari, ish joyidagi xavf-xatarlarni baholash, sanoat gigiyenasi, shaxsiy himoya vositalari, baxtsiz hodisalarning oldini olish hamda raqamli texnologiyalarni qo‘llash, ilmiy-nazariy va amaliy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Mehnat muhofazasi tizimining asosiy komponentlari, xavf omillarini aniqlash va baholash usullari, shuningdek, favqulodda vaziyatlarning oldini olishda zamonaviy yondashuvlar ko‘rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqot davomida normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar, ilg‘or xorijiy tajribalar va ishlab chiqarishdagi real holatlar asosida tahliliy xulosalar chiqariladi. Natijalar mehnat sharoitlarini yaxshilash, ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarida xavfsizlik madaniyatini oshirish hamda barqaror rivojlanishni ta’minlashga xizmat qiladi.

Tayanch so‘zlar: mehnat muhofazasi, ishlab chiqarish xavfsizligi, texnosfera xavfsizligi, xavf omillari, ishlab chiqarish xavfsizligi, favqulodda vaziyatlar

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ЗАЩИТЕ ТРУДА И НЕПРЕРЫВНОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ

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В области охраны труда и технической безопасности.

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Аннотация. В данной статье обсуждаются вопросы охраны труда и обеспечения постоянной безопасности в производственной и обслуживающей сферах, трудовое законодательство, правила техники безопасности, оценка рисков на рабочем месте, промышленная гигиена, средства индивидуальной защиты, предупреждение несчастных случаев и применение цифровых технологий, научно-теоретический и практический анализ. Будут рассмотрены основные компоненты системы охраны труда, методы выявления и оценки факторов риска, а также современные подходы в

предупреждении чрезвычайных ситуаций. В ходе исследования будут сделаны аналитические выводы на основе нормативно-правовых актов, передового зарубежного опыта и реальных условий производства. Результаты будут способствовать улучшению условий труда, повышению культуры безопасности в производственных процессах и обеспечению устойчивого развития.

Ключевые слова: охрана труда, безопасность производства, техносферная безопасность, факторы риска, производственная безопасность.

INTRODUCTION.

Today, the complexity of technological processes in production and service industries, the introduction of new techniques and equipment are making labor protection and ensuring constant safety an urgent problem. The relevance of labor protection is determined by the need to carry out measures aimed at maintaining the safety, health and working capacity of people in the labor process. Control over the implementation of the requirements of labor protection legislation is carried out by special state bodies and society. In cases of non-compliance with the requirements of the legislation, financial and economic measures are applied to enterprises, and their officials may be required to bear administrative, legal, criminal liability and compensation for material damage. In the conditions of the technosphere, the increase in risk factors associated with human activity is leading to the occurrence of accidents, occupational diseases and emergency situations in the production process. Therefore, improving the labor protection system and ensuring continuous safety is one of the important areas of modern scientific research.

Main part.

Labor protection is a set of laws, regulations and organizational measures aimed at ensuring the protection of workers from potential hazards in the labor process.

The basis of the Labor Protection Law: regulation of relations in the field of labor protection, the employer's obligation to comply with labor protection requirements and standards, the right of workers to have jobs that meet labor protection requirements and standards, the right of workers to receive information from the employer about working conditions, the right of workers to be provided with personal protective equipment, the employer's obligation to ensure labor protection requirements at workplaces, the employer's obligation to stop work in cases where there is a threat to the life and health of workers, etc. Basic principles of labor protection:

- Ensuring safety: Identifying, assessing and eliminating hazards in the workplace.

- Healthy working conditions: Normalizing temperature, lighting, noise and dust levels in the workplace.

- Personal protective equipment: Providing employees with modern protective equipment (respirators, helmets, special clothing).

- Technical safety and industrial hygiene:

- Monitoring the safety of machines and equipment.

- Increasing safety through automation and digitalization (for example, digital control of work processes).

- Measures to prevent accidents and occupational diseases.

- The role of digital technologies:

- Digitalization of labor protection instructions, distance learning (electronic courses).

Real-time monitoring of workplace safety (using sensors, drones). If we analyze the current state of the problem, the current analysis of scientific literature shows that although many manufacturing enterprises have labor protection systems, their practical effectiveness is insufficient [1,2]. In particular, the weakness of mechanisms for early identification and assessment of risk factors, the low culture

of compliance with safety rules by employees, and the obsolescence of technical safety equipment cause negative situations in the production process.

Foreign studies have proven that the organization of safety management systems based on an integrated approach reduces the number of accidents in production [3,4]. However, the implementation of these approaches in local conditions has not been sufficiently studied.

Problem statement: For this, taking into account the problems listed above, the main task of this study is to identify effective mechanisms aimed at ensuring labor protection and constant safety in production processes. The study was based on the requirements of the regulatory legal acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan on labor protection and international standards (ISO 45001). The main goal is to develop scientifically based solutions that serve to reduce risk factors, protect employee health, and increase production efficiency.

The solution method used in the research process was systematic analysis, statistical data processing, and comparative analysis to identify and assess risks. Physical, chemical and ergonomic hazards in the production environment were identified and their impact on human health was assessed.

The effectiveness of training sessions aimed at improving the knowledge and skills of employees in order to improve the safety management system was also studied. The selected methods were described in sufficient detail to be applicable to other researchers.

Results. In the process of analyzing the research results, the main risk factors encountered in the production environment and their impact on the labor process were identified.

Table 1

The level of impact of risk factors in production processes

Type of risk factor	Meeting rate
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Mechanical hazards	High
Electrical hazards	Average
Chemical factors	Low
Ergonomic hazards	High

The results show that mechanical and ergonomic risk factors are the most common and have a significant impact on human health in the production process. Therefore, updating safety equipment and ergonomic improvement of workplaces is of great importance.

A direct relationship between the level of knowledge of employees on labor protection and compliance with safety rules has been established, and the number of emergencies has significantly decreased in teams where regular training sessions were held [5–8].

The results of the analysis showed that an integrated and systematic approach to ensuring safety is highly effective.

CONCLUSION.

The conducted studies have shown that ensuring labor protection and continuous safety is crucial for protecting the rights of employees and increasing the efficiency of the enterprise. The interdependence of labor protection, the responsibility of each employee in creating a safe working environment and the responsibility of the employee. is of decisive importance in protecting life and health. The results can be implemented in practice and serve as a scientific basis for improving the safety management system. Regular training of employees, identification and assessment of risk factors, as well as the creation of ergonomic working conditions help to increase the safety culture.

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